

MODERN CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS (CRM'S) IMPLEMENTATION AND IMMEDIATE EFFECTS ANALYSIS ON SME'S

Author(s)*: Tudor FARAGAU ¹, Oliviu MATEI ², Laura BACALI ³, Monica BOGDAN ⁴
Position: PhD Student¹, Prof., PhD², Prof., PhD³, PhD Student⁴
University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Address: Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului Str., No. 28, Romania
Email: tudor.faragau@mis.utcluj.ro ¹, oliviu.matei@cunbm.utcluj.ro², laura.bacali@mis.utcluj.ro³,
t.monica@yahoo.com⁴
Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro>

Abstract

Purpose – Our paper looks into the main characteristics of modern CRMs and analyze the implementation stage and immediate effect analysis in 10 diverse Romanian SMEs in a post COVID-19 world.

Methodology/approach – The research team conducted a semi structured questionnaire with 10 executive managers and used personal observations, through studying the reactions before and after CRM implementation.

Research limitations/implications – Only SME's which implemented the AIDA CRM solution since 2019 were selected as case studies, so that the interviewed managers have a fresher perspective on post-implementation organizational changes and the immediate effects of CRM implementation during the pandemic.

Practical implications – Modern CRMs have the ability to increase business profitability and streamline workflows, automating various tasks and achieving team synergies, in order to increase organizational performance and efficiency.

Originality/value – The current research gap, considered a missing piece in the research literature, is the area that determines the process and benefits of implementing a modern CRM for Romanian SMEs. Therefore, through this scientific paper we analyzed the determinants of a modern CRM implementation and analyze the immediate benefits in 10 Romanian SME's, each operating in a different field of activity.

Key words: Customer Relationship Management.

Introduction

Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic using a Customer Relationship Management System (CRM) was seen as something to be implemented by large enterprises, usually Romanian SME's being more skeptical in regards to it's benefits.

However, the rapid migration of traditional brick and mortar clients in the digital economy, simultaneously with strict social distancing regulations imposed by the pandemic has created an urgent requirement for more SME's to evolve and start using digital business solutions in order to work from a distance and serve digital clients, so the question arose, are solutions such as CRM's worth the investment for SME's?

A significant contribution to our modern business approach of seeing retention costs of clients as being less expensive than acquiring new ones was made by Reichheld, Markey, Hopton (2000) which inspired a series of customer retention strategies that were incorporated and automated into the digital systems known today as "Customer Relationship Management", according to Roberts, Liu, and Hazard (2005).

Nowadays, modern CRMs have the ability to increase profitability and streamline workflows, automating various tasks and achieving team synergies, in order to increase organizational performance and efficiency.

Because the needs of every business are so diverse, from strategic, operational, analytical, employee collaboration or customer data platforms, there are hundreds of CRM solutions on the market, tailored to fit the multiple needs of diverse businesses.

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the commercial offering of various types of CRMs, as well as numerous scientific articles, which shows that a CRM is necessary to ensure long-term business sustainability, such studies are seen in the works of authors such as: Chang (2007), Shanks, Jagielska, Jayaganesh (2009), Loh, Koo, Ho, Idrus (2011), Nahar, Dhaka (2014), and many others.

Customer relationship management is widely regarded as an essential business philosophy that focuses on retaining and improving customers. "Successful implementation of CRM results in reduced customer dropout rates, reduced costs, and increased revenue", according to Yee-Man Siu [2016].

However, the literature largely deals with the benefits of CRM implementation by large enterprises, but there are significant fewer studies on the benefits of CRM implementation in the small business sector and even fewer studies on the impact of CRM systems on Romania SMEs.

The current research gap, considered a missing piece in the research literature, is the area that determines the process and benefits of implementing a modern CRM for Romanian SMEs.

Our paper aims to see how a modern and adaptable CRM has created added value in 10 different areas of activity, by analyzing the challenges in the implementation process and analyzing the immediate effects and benefits of implementing CRM's for 10 Romanian SME's, each from a different field of activity, as follows: Tax Consulting, Grants Consulting, B2B Sales (Business to Business), Architecture Studio, Sales B2C (Business to Clients), Topography, Medical Office, Software Development.

Research methodology

The research conducted a semi structured questionnaire with 10 executive managers and used personal observations, through studying the reactions before and after CRM implementation, from a personal perspective, as members and partners of the Holisun team that made the 10 CRM configurations.

Because we worked with business informations that are considered sensitive by some entrepreneurs surveyed in the study, we will not publicly disclose the names of those 10 companies.

Only SMEs that have implemented the AIDA CRM solution in 2019-2020 were selected as case studies, so that the managers interviewed have a fresher perspective on post-implementation organizational changes and the immediate effects of CRM implementation.

The questions included in the semi-structured interview are the ones from the following Table 1.

Implementation analysis

1. Tax consulting company

About the company

Founding: Founded in 2005 in Baia Mare, Maramures County.

Specialization: transfer pricing consulting services, one of the most important companies with 100% Romanian capital operating in this sector.

Background: hired the first employee in 2010, in 2019 the company reached 21 employees, a gross income of 6.4 million lei (approx. 1.3 million EUR), and has a portfolio of 55 clients, consisting mainly of multinational companies (foreign and domestic).

Why did they need a CRM?

Most of the 21 employees specialize in providing transfer pricing consulting services, and 3 of these employees handle back-office operations, such as managing contracts, invoices and other day-to-day administrative activities.

They needed a CRM for the back-office operations team that manages administrative operations related to the company's clients.

Table 1. Interview questions for entrepreneurs. Source: Author

Question	Type of answer
1. What was the main reason for implementing a CRM?	Open answer
2. How much did it cost to implement CRM?	Open answer
3. How do you estimate the cost of CRM?	Open answer
4. How many customers do you have?	Open answer
5. How many employees manage these customers?	Open answer
6. Is there a difference between the number of employees involved in customer management, according to CRM?	Yes/No
7. What was the average customer satisfaction feedback before implementing CRM?	More than one answer: a) I have not used any feedback system before CRM b) 1-2 points c) 2-3 points d) 3-4 points e) 4-5 points
8. Has there been a positive monthly increase in customer feedback since the implementation of CRM?	More than one answer: a) No, there has been a decrease in customer satisfaction b) 1 points c) 2 points d) 3 points e) 4 points
9. Was there a monthly increase in target performance (sales, projects, etc.) per employee after CRM implementation?	More than one answer: a) Nu, results are the same b) Nu, results are weaker than before c) Yes, of 5-10% d) Yes, of 10-20% e) Yes, of 30-40% f) Yes, more than 40%
10. How long did it take to implement the custom CRM solution?	a) 1 luna b) 2 months c) 3 months d) 4 months e) 5 months f) 6 months g) more than 6 months
11. What were the main drawbacks in CRM implementation?	Open answer
12. If you've used CRM in the past, why would you want another CRM?	Open answer

How the CRM implementation went?

There were 2 preliminary online meetings between the general manager of the company, the 3 employees of support operations and development team of AIDA CRM, in which the first meeting was aimed at presenting the general platform AIDA CRM and obtaining feedback on what can be used from the AIDA CRM platform and which would be further developed to suit the particular needs of the company.

The second meeting dealt with the adaptation requirements and the resources that the company needs to provide in order to start the CRM platform configuration project.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

Three months after the implementation of AIDA CRM, the tax consulting company registered a 1-point improvement in customer satisfaction, thanks to the "external ticket" function within the CRM, through which customer requests were automatically segmented into low-importance / medium / urgent priority, so the human resources dedicated to their solution could be allocated more efficiently, depending on the urgency of each request (emergency requests - settlement time 2 hours; medium requests – settlement time 8 hours; low requests - resolution time 16 hours).

Due to the external ticket functionality within the CRM platform, the company records an average customer satisfaction feedback higher by 1 point out of 5 after the implementation of the CRM, according to the statement of the General Manager.

b) Employee productivity

As most of the repetitive work of the support operations team was automated, such as invoicing, document generation, such as contracts and business offers, the efficiency of those 3 employees increased by 10-20 %, according to the company's General Manager.

CRM price and value perception

The CRM platform was implemented for the tax consulting company with few special configurations, in this sense the company had to pay only a SaaS (Software as a Service) subscription fee of 90 euros / month for the 3 users of the operations department support (30 euros per user).

2. Grants consulting company

About the company

Founding: Founded in 2007 by a single shareholder in Cluj-Napoca, Cluj County.

Specialization: The company specializes in providing consulting services related to accessing non-reimbursable funds for clusters as well as cluster management services, managing 3 of the largest clusters in the Transylvania region.

Background:

Hired its first employee in 2008, now the team consists of 4 employees and 16 collaborators who are paid according to the number of hours worked in projects and commission depending on results.

In 2019, the turnover of the company were around 500,000 lei (aprox. 100.000 EUR), but the company is also the beneficiary of several European non-reimbursable funds, for which the amounts received are not seen as turnover, but as state aid.

Why did they need a CRM?

Recently, it has become increasingly important to audit the work done by collaborators for each client, as clients usually pay a fixed amount for consulting services, but the costs for external consultants were variable depending on the number of clients, hours worked on projects, which until recently were not properly audited.

In this regard, after an internal analysis was conducted in the company, it was decided that the implementation of a customized CRM is the best way to audit the working hours spent on projects and improve communication within the company, in order to increase productivity.

How the CRM implementation went

The implementation process was a challenging one, as the standard CRM project management module had to be rebuilt according to the company's needs, as well as developing of a special time control function within the project management module.

The implementation process took about 15 business days, but the project was delivered in 3 months due to the limited resources of the CRM platform developer.

Results after implementation

The implementation of AIDA CRM was a success as all the technical requirements of the company were met and the delivery was made before the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced the company's employees and collaborators to work remote and thus work exclusively through the CRM.

a) Customer satisfaction

There was an increase in customer satisfaction by 1 point out of 5, customers appreciated the change, by the fact that the CRM provided a lot of important information about projects, projects that could be viewed by employees, collaborators and customers. According to the General Manager of the company, without the implementation of CRM, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, it would have been difficult to imagine that the project deadlines would have been met, when all employees and collaborators had to work exclusively from home.

b) Employee productivity

A positive result of the quarantine imposed by COVID-19 was that employees and collaborators were more willing to use the CRM platform, having no other virtual work environment available for project management, even if the implementation of CRM meant greater transparency regarding the actual number of hours worked.

After implementation, the productivity of those 20 employees and collaborators increased by 5-10 %, and customer feedback also improved by 1 point out of 5, due to the transparency of the projects and the function of external tickets that prioritize requests from customers, which meant the ability to respond more quickly to requests for real client urgency.

CRM price and value perception

The company decided to rent a custom made CRM solution, by paying a monthly SaaS subscription of 15 euros per user, or 300 euros in total / month.

The company is satisfied with the price of the subscription in relation to the increased productivity after the implementation of the CRM platform, productivity according to the General Manager increased between 5-10 % in a difficult period in which employees and collaborators who were forced to work exclusively from home. The CEO believes that productivity will continue to rise after employees and collaborators return to the office.

3. B2B Sales company

About the company

Founding: Founded in 2008 with a single shareholder in Dej, Cluj County.

Specialization: largest business to business distributor of Dutch tulips in the Transylvania region, serving over 600 B2B customers from local florists to large retailers, such as the Auchan Romania hypermarket chain.

Background:

The company runs as a family business, the general manager's son-in-law running the warehouse in Dej, Cluj Country, the general manager's daughter being the operational director, and the general manager running the business from the companies public office from Cluj-Napoca, Cluj Country.

In 2019 the company registered a gross income of 6.5 million lei (aprox. 1.3 million EURO) with 8 employees, out of which: 4 warehouse employees, 2 sales agents, an operational director and a general manager.

Why did they need a CRM?

Dutch tulips are some of the most beautiful tulips on the Romanian market, but if the tulips are not sold before they reach the warehouse in Dej where they are rapidly distributed in Transylvania, they must be sold quickly at a discount or even discarded, being perishable products, with a short shelf life.

The company needed to implement a CRM to move from the simple Ecommerce site used to take a significant proportion of total orders to a CRM used by the 600 B2B customers-operational manager-supplier-warehouse-distribution for getting all orders in one place, aggregate those orders by size, categorize them and notify the Dutch tulip supplier when the order can be shipped, in order for them to collect the tulips and arrange transportation to the warehouse in Dej, from where they are distributed to clients in the Transylvania region.

How the CRM implementation went?

The project, more complex than a regular CRM customization, went smoothly as the technical needs were clearly established by the beneficiary and the project manager promptly answered all technical questions of the AIDA CRM development team.

The 600 B2B customers had no problem adapting to CRM, as they were used to ordering from the old E-Commerce platforms, where CRM automatically took the orders, the warehouse manager also liked the CRM platform, as it saw an improvement in warehouse management, through more efficient logistical communication with the Dutch supplier and Romanian customers.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

A point of improvement of the feedback was noticed after the CRM was implemented together with its own integrated automatic feedback system. B2B customers could now provide feedback after each received order with just click on a star directly in an email sent by the CRM, such as " *, **, ***, ****, ***** " (5 points meaning excellent service).

Because management does not believe that the quality of the tulip was improved after the implementation of CRM, we assume that the mere fact that the company requested feedback via e-mail improved the perception of after-sales quality.

b) Employee productivity

The biggest increase in productivity after the implementation of CRM is that of the operations director who had time to "breathe" and avoid past mistakes in the ordering procedure to the dutch supplier.

The operations director told us that 30 to 40% of her daily work was automated, thanks to the CRM platform.

CRM price and value perception

Due to the extensive customization required for CRM, the SaaS subscription option was not available, so the customer paid 5,000 euros for a CRM license, the amount was paid in 6 monthly installments at the customer's request.

The implementation of the project required 35 working days by the AIDA CRM team. However, the project was implemented in 6 months, the client not being able to assign a project manager until the fall of 2019.

4. Architecture Studio

About the company

Founded: in 2000 as a family business by husband and wife, both experienced architects.

Specialization: residential and commercial architectural design, as well as in the management of construction projects

Background:

In 2019, the company registered total gross income of approximately 1 million lei (aprox. 200.000 EUR) with 7 employees.

The day-to-day operations are run by the wife, and the husband is the one who negotiates contracts and manages the largest clients in the fields of residential development and office spaces.

Why did they need a CRM?

As the company began hiring young and inexperienced architects, they had issues characteristic to young and inexperienced employees.

The young architects did not pay as much attention to administrative issues associated with architectural projects, as when a building permit expired and must be extended, the young architects lacked knowledge of the various special documentation flows for each type of project, such as dwelling extension, urban planning permits, authorization from the monument authority, etc.

This type of problems created tensions between the management and the younger employees, as those mistakes delayed projects, leading to fines, low productivity and morale.

The company needed a CRM to generate email and mobile text messages alerts so that young architects could be more organized and see when a permit expires, what kind of documents and special permits are required for each type of project, how to better manage projects, improve internal communication and most importantly avoid costly delays in time and money for customers.

How the CRM implementation went?

A significant number of meetings were required as the the AIDA customization framework was developed in partnership with the architecture studio, as there were a lot of special workflows that needed to be built within the CRM platform.

In order to help younger architects better manage their projects and also ensure increased productivity by using the CRM project management module, it was necessary to create templates for each type of architectural project and so over 80 types of project documentation templates were created in the CRM.

The company also needed time to digitize the customers database, as well as training employees to trust and contribute to the configuration of the CRM. It took a total of 42 working days to complete the project.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

The company does not keep a clear record of customer satisfaction, as most of the company's architectural projects take more than 6 months. But, as employees are using the CRM platform to avoid making the common mistakes in the past, we can assume that this will have an positive impact in terms of organizational efficiency as well as customer satisfaction.

b) Employee productivity

The implementation of the CRM is still very new for an architecture studio, where the results will be seen in a longer time span, but the preliminary results are encouraging.

There was a 10-20% increase in productivity in the first month after implementation, the companies however believes that the highest productivity possible, can happen only if besides using the CRM, local authorities will accept digital documents and online appoints, so that valuable working time will not be spent waiting at various public institutions queues, in order to submit urban documentation, such as the City Hall, the County Council, the Environmental Authority, the Monuments Authority, etc. The increase in productivity was mainly due to not making mistakes, due to lack of experience and knowing how to properly prepare the 80 types of project documentations.

CRM price and value perception

The aquisition was seen as a good and not to expensive investment, given the increase in internal efficiency for the younger architects in the company.

5. Facility Management

About the company

Founded: In 2019, in Timisoara by a young entrepreneur through a "StartUp Nation"¹ government grant.

Specialization: housecleaning for residential and offices

Background:

¹ About StartUp Nation grants: <http://www.imm.gov.ro/ro/mmaca-etichete/startup-proiect>

The company had 41 clients in 2019 from private residential areas to office spaces, which are served by 5 employees, including the General Manager who manages administrative operations and sales.

Why did they need a CRM?

In addition to high-performance cleaning machines, which undoubtedly contributed to the productivity of the 4 employees who perform day to day cleaning operations, there is also a large volume of administrative operations, such as managing appointments and responding to requests from a growing number of customers which does not leave much time for conducting prospecting activities, which is also the responsibility of the General Manager (CEO).

The company thus needed a CRM that would automate routine customer communication and be a tool for these customers in order for them to self schedule the desired visits from the facility management company, thus decongesting the appointment activity carried out by the General Manager, manager who also needs the CRM in order to manage prospecting activities for new customers.

How the CRM implementation went

The company's technical needs were easy to implement, and the project was in line with the company's long-term strategy to have the most automated and modern facility management business possible on the local market. In order to carry out the CRM implementation process which lasted 3 working days, it was necessary to have 3 online meetings between the General Manager and the CRM implementation team.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

After CRM implementation, customers quickly got used to the online programming tool inside the CRM and appreciated the new online programming facility. However their satisfaction did not increase significantly, given that their satisfaction was rather related to the quality of the cleaning service.

b) Employee productivity

After the implementation of the CRM, the company's productivity increased by 10-20 % and there was significantly less managerial involvement in the day-to-day management of customers. The General Manager used the extra time to develop prospecting activities within the CRM platform.

Using advanced marketing tools (Mass Marketing) in CRM, such as the sending a large number of predetermined mobile text messages and e-mails, both with tracking functions, the General Manager was able to carry out more advanced prospecting activities in order to attract new customers directly through the CRM and achieve more efficient management of the sales funnel.

The CEO was also able to create automated invoices from the CRM, which were sent automatically to clients and also create automated documents, such as contracts and business offers, using document templates, which saved valuable time, time now allocated to prospecting activities.

CRM price and value perception In the first stage, the cost of the monthly SaaS subscription (Software as a Service) of 60 euros seemed expensive to the CEO, but after the CRM was implemented and the manager has seen the benefits of CRM, the price was considered appropriate.

6. Law firm

About the company

Founded: in 2016, Cluj Napoca.

Specialization: practices law in the fields of companies, insolvency, insurance, administrative and tax, consumer protection, intellectual property, telecommunications and IT.

Background:

The Law firm has 9 collaborators, and a founding member which serve a portfolio of 108 clients, from which you can find prestigious Romanian companies and personalities.

The founding member of the law firm is also a strong supporter of digital innovation in law firms, and as a result, the law firm has already tried many CRM solutions built specifically for lawyers.

The company needed a more versatile solution than AvoApp, the previous solution used which could:
synchronize lawyers' calendars in "Google Calendar".

provide a more advanced solution in terms of customer legal processes

grant restricted access to clients through a client portal within the CRM, so that they can see their own legal processes and communicate with the lawyer(s) managing their legal case.

reduce repetitive work of lawyers as much as possible by automating repetitive operations, such as sending invoices, writing commercial contracts or business offers.

How the CRM implementation went?

Since the company's founder knew in detail what a CRM is and had previous experience with other CRM solutions, the technical discussion was very straightforward.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction did not increase, as the overall results in the courtroom are what ultimately determines customer satisfaction in a law firm. Even though customer satisfaction did not improve after the CRM was implemented, most clients recognized the implementation of the CRM as a positive aspect in terms of conducting business with the law firm.

b) Employee productivity

The founder of the law firm and the other 8 collaborators were delighted with the new CRM, which they saw as more versatile than the previous CRMs, being completely configured according to their needs.

Productivity within the company increased by 10-20 %, and most of the productivity was represented by time saved, such as time not wasted discussing unimportant issues with clients on the phone, these discussions are now taking place to some extent through the CRM's client portal, which has led to a more efficient way of communication with clients.

Productivity also increased due to the reduction of repetitive work through the use of e-mail templates and email automation, as well as the creation of document templates (contracts, business offers, powers of attorney annex, etc.) and existence of client tickets in the CRM.

CRM price and value perception

The company went for a SaaS subscription fee of 135 euros/month or 15 euros/month per user.

The monthly subscription costs 50 % more than the cost of the old AvoApp subscription, but as productivity increases in the company by 10-20 %, the company manager considers the investment a profitable one.

7. B2C Sales

About the company

Founding: in 2005 in Bistrita County, as a family business.

Specialization: business to clients (B2C) telecommunication sales subscriptions (TV, Internet, Mobile Services) in rural areas.

Background:

The telecommunications professional who founded the company, now 55, has retired from business and his son started running the company from 2014.

The company's revenues have been on an upward trend since 2005 and in 2019 reached a gross income of 2.5 million lei (aprox. 500.000 euros). The company began to expand rapidly to 30 employees in 2016, when the company signed a representation agreement with a major telecommunications player for exclusive B2C sales in Bistrita County. The agreement meant that in the rural areas of Bistrita-Nasaud there will be no other company allowed to sell the B2C subscriptions for that telecommunications company.

As the company expanded from 1 employee in 2015 to 30 employees in 2019, serving thousand of households, it became very difficult to manage expenses and coordinate the 30 employees, 15 of whom were local sales representatives.

Why did they need a CRM?

The company needed a CRM to coordinate the sales team that sold B2C subscriptions for telecommunication services, to manage the growing customer base and, in general, have better control over the operational part of the company.

As many of the 15 sales staff live in rural areas, face-to-face meetings with the manager were rare, so a CRM was needed to coordinate sales and provide support when needed.

How the CRM implementation went

CRM implementation was technically not difficult to implement, but there were issues regarding the sales team being reluctant to use the CRM platform.

Even though the project was supposed to last 4 days, a total of approximately 9 working days were allocated for the project and 2 months of extended training assistance in order to ensure that the CRM is fully understood by all employees.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction increased by 1 point out of 5. Increased customer satisfaction was associated with the fact that the sales team's telephone dialing decreased significantly, with a large amount communication activities with customers migrating to emails and mobile text messages.

Younger customers preferring informal and digital communication options, perceiving sales calls by salespeople as an annoying and aggressive communication technique.

b) Employee productivity

After implementation and acceptance by employees, the CRM was a huge success, as employees started receiving alerts at the expiration date of old contracts for renewal purposes and automatic cross-selling campaigns were implemented. Contracts could also be generated instantly so that employees will no longer waste time writing them by hand.

The manager was able to coordinate the entire sales team and sales campaigns through the CRM "Dashboard" and was also able to carry out human resources operations, such as approving leave requests through the CRM.

After implementation, the company's productivity increased by 30-40% by automating and streamlining many sales activities.

CRM price and value perception

The monthly subscription for CRM was 300 euros per month or 10 euros / month per user. The perception of the value of the cost associated with implementing CRM is more than satisfactory,

in the opinion of the CEO, as he said in his statement: "Now that I have a CRM, I don't see the possibility of going back. I think the CRM was one of the best investments I've ever made. CEO"

8. Topography

About the company

Founding: in 2016 in Baia Mare, Maramures, County by a young geological engineer.

Specialization: geological and geodetic engineering for ground surveying, photogrammetry, cadastre and geotechnics services.

Background:

The activity started with 4 young employees in the field of geological and geodetic engineering.

Currently, the company serves an average 32 customers with 6 employees. The company registered in 2019 a gross income of around 325.000 lei (aprox. 66.000 EUR).

Why did they need a CRM?

The company needed a CRM to better communicate with customers without wasting time in numerous non productive meetings and telephone conversations.

Also, the implementation of the CRM was considered necessary to avoid the risk of employees forgetting important things such as the expiration date of an authorization approved by the city hall, a need similar to the ones seen in the previous architecture studio analysis.

A more specific need of the topographic company that justified the implementation of the CRM platform is that each team member manages around 6 projects, each employee having to prioritize those projects as best as possible, as certain types of authorization were granted. The company's management considered that the need for a CRM could help employees to identify in advance which projects should be prioritized, following through the CRM the expiring authorizations and those to be granted for various works.

The implementation process went smoothly and there was little customization involved. It took about 4 business days to configure the CRM to the company's needs, but the project was started 2 months late due to the manager's busy schedule.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

After a period of implementation and adaptation that lasted about a month, customer calls began to be transformed into internal tickets within the CRM, customers quickly getting used to this way of working, and the company changed it's communication policy, by communicating project updates with customers directly and only through the client portal inside the CRM, customers could now track their project completion and communicate with the topography employees directly through the chat box inside the CRM client portal.

Customer satisfaction has significantly improved by 2 points out of 5 points. Increasing customer satisfaction in this case had to do with improving customer communication by creating the CRM customer portal.

b) Employee productivity

According to the manager, in addition to improving customer satisfaction, internal productivity increased by 10-20% within the company.

The increase in employee productivity by 10-20 % had to do with 2 main factors:

Clients can now receive project updates in CRM, there is no need for employees to be constantly on the phone with customers, and vice versa.

Employees receive a mobile text message and an email alert when a notice is about to expire and needs to be renewed.

CRM price and value perception

The manager considers that the monthly SaaS subscription of 75 euros was expensive, but in the end it was worth it, because CRM has significantly improved communication with customers without wasting unnecessary time in countless meetings and phone calls, which reduced risks, such as forgetting important events, like the date when an authorization approved by the mayor's office expires.

9. Medical office

About the company

Founding: in 2005 in Cluj-Napoca by a young doctor of occupational medicine.

Specialization: occupational medicine.

Background:

The company in 2019 registered 220 recurring B2B clients, a gross income of 460.000 lei (aprox. 93.000 EUR) with the help of 5 employees, of which a medical office manager, 3 occupational physicians and a psychologist.

Why did they need a CRM?

As the medical office specializes in occupational medicine, which means dozens of occupational health consulting services every day/per doctor, it was considered necessary to streamline the repetitive operations activities of the clinic manager, such as setting up consulting appointments (office and in the field) and billing activities.

In this sense, a CRM in which the appointments are made by the client and invoicing is done automatically, would lead to a lower workload of the office manager, which means more time to more productive activities.

How the CRM implementation went?

The implementation process lasted 1 month, of which 5 days of actual work for the CRM platform implementation team.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

The medical office does not ask for feedback on a medical service provided, also the CRM was implemented more for internal reasons and not to increase customer satisfaction. The medical office only estimates that their services are perceived as good to excellent. There were no perceived changes in customer satisfaction after the implementation of the CRM.

b) Employee productivity

After the implementation of CRM, there was a significant improvement in the number of hours involved in managing customer scheduling, as well as in the time allocated to billing activities.

After the implementation of CRM, there was an increase in the efficiency of the medical office's management activity between 10-20 %, the clinic manager no longer having as much administrative work as in the past.

CRM price and value perception

At a 50 euro monthly SaaS subscription, the cost of implementing the CRM was seen as a good investment, as the productivity associated with administrative activities increased by 10-20%.

10. Software Development

About the company

Founding: in 2005 in Bucharest, in the form of a business partnership between a Romanian business woman and a French businessman.

Specialization: accounting software company

Background:

In 2019, the company reached a gross income of 6.7 million lei (aprox. 1.35 million EUR) through over 800 customers served by only 49 employees, most employees working in the maintenance and sales department. The company has two revenue streams, from the sale of software licenses and maintenance services to customers.

Why did they need a CRM?

The company had in the past implemented MiniCRM², a standardized CRM, but the implemented platform could not be adapted to generate special reports for sales and customer maintenance which have been requested by the client.

How the CRM implementation went?

The technical discussion was from one software provider to another, which is why technical aspects in regards to the CRM configuration was rapidly discussed. The actual working time for configuring the platform to the needs of the company took 15 working days.

Results after implementation

a) Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction increased by 1 point out of 5 after the implementation of the new CRM. Improving customer satisfaction is seen as an indirect benefit of streamlining internal work procedures, as the CRM provided more information to management about customers, the maintenance department and the sales department. With more complex data and reports, the CRM resolved internal bottlenecks and this in turn improved customer satisfaction.

b) Employee productivity

After the CRM implementation, the 30 employees in sales and technical support enjoyed an increase in productivity of approximately 5-10%.

CRM price and value perception

The CRM was offered in the form of a SaaS subscription of 450 euros per month or 15 euros per user. The company did not have a problem with the investment, being a price similar to the cost of the old CRM previously implemented.

Conclusions

After the CRM implementation, all the companies interviewed recorded an increase in productivity, as shown in Table 2.

² MiniCRM website: <https://www.minicrm.ro>

Productivity

The slightest increase in productivity of 5-10% was observed in the software developer, because it has already started to use a CRM before the implementation of the new AIDA CRM solution, which also generated some improvements in organizational performance.

Table 2. Results after CRM implementation. Source: Author

Case studiu	Field of activity	Employees	Clients	Productivity	Client satisfaction
7	B2C Sales	15	1200	30-40%	1
3	B2B Sales	8	600	30-40%	1
1	Tax consulting company	3	55	10-20%	1
4	Arhitecture studio	8	28	10-20%	0
5	Facility Management	3	21	10-20%	1
6	Law firm	9	108	10-20%	0
8	Topography	6	32	10-20%	2
9	Medical cabinet	5	220	10-20%	0
10	Software development	30	800	5-10%	1
2	Grants consulting company	20	120	5-10%	1

A slower increase in productivity was also seen in the grants consulting firm that implemented the CRM during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the case of the grants consulting firm, we believe that productivity did not increase so much during the COVID-19 period, because the CRM was implemented in the stress induced lockdown period when employees out of whom many parents also needed to take care of their children that started to study from home.

Six of the companies analyzed increased their productivity by 10-20% through a combination of automated sales and marketing workflows and the use of digital productivity tools such as tickets, control time, emails with automatic templates, automatic document generation, etc.

In the case of the B2B sales company, productivity increased significantly by 30-40 % on the operational side because most of the buy/sell orders managed by the operational manager could now be fully automated.

In the B2B sales company, productivity improved only in terms of internal operations and not in sales, with sales agents rejecting the use of the CRM platform, for fear of increased transparency and oversight by management.

The productivity of the B2C telecommunication sales company also increased by 30-40%, and the manager was able to better coordinate and supervise the sales team in the rural area of Bistrita-Nasaud. Also, the manager and sales staff could now use the advanced digital methods of prospecting and retention performed directly through the CRM.

The factors that improved the productivity of the 10 case studies ranged from extra time gained by automating administrative activities, such as the case of the medical office, or increasing organizational performance through the existence of automated sales workflows, such as the software developer and B2C telecommunications sales company.

Client satisfaction

The increase in internal productivity also increased the perception of customer satisfaction in 7 of the 10 SME's analyzed. Of the 7 companies, 6 increased their customer satisfaction rate by 1 point (out of 5), and in the case of the topography company we saw an increase in customer satisfaction by 2 points (out of 5).

The increase in customer satisfaction in the 10 case studies is due to one or more of the following factors:

Better communication with clients. In the case of the B2B sales company, the law firm, the grants consultant and the topography company, the reason for implementing CRM was to increase internal efficiency, not customer satisfaction, but increasing internal productivity and transparency between employees, indirectly impacted customers satisfaction, as customers perceived that each of those companies began to offer higher quality services, by being internally more efficient.

In the case of the topography and law firms, the only thing that changed in relation to customers was better external communication, as customers could use a customer portal inside the CRM, a portal where they could view information about the status of their projects. In this regard, we can argue that customers treat digital communication as a service that companies should provide.

Improving internal processes In the modern age, we truly live in a fast-paced world where CRMs can be an important partner for any company that wants to serve its customers better and more efficiently. By improving internal workflows, the B2B sales company, the software development company, the B2C sales company and the law firm serve their customer base better, faster and smarter due to improvements in business processes, which required both the existence of CRM-type IT platforms as well as adapting the way of doing business in the digital age, or rather the digitization of business processes.

Better - do not contact customers by phone to buy things, but rather use segmentation, strategic reporting, and customer sales history to anticipate the individual needs of each customer (a customer who buys product A is usually interested in product B; a customer usually buys a new product A after 1 year from the purchase of the previous product or similar to product A, etc). In addition, making things better means knowing and taking into account each customer's preferred ways of communicating and knowing the sales channels that these customers use. Some clients want to go to the showroom alone and do not want any form of proactive communication, others prefer to be contacted only by email, other clients are more receptive to business proposals in face-to-face meetings, etc.

Faster - in the modern world of instant gratification and with a young generation accustomed to ordering a product via E-Commerce and receiving that product within 24 hours, ordering food via a mobile app, and receiving delivery within 15 minutes, we can say for certain that customer satisfaction is becoming more and more difficult to achieve in the digital economy. Whether a CRM is used to control and adapt the business strategy to the needs of the modern customer, seen in the case of the analyzed B2C telecommunication company, or to sell products faster, such as the case of the seller of fresh tulips, we must constantly think of new ways to be faster, and CRMs are proving to be good tools in this regard, by automating repetitive work and creating digital business flows that are much faster and makes the business more scalable.

Smarter - having as much relevant data as possible about internal business processes, competition and customers in a single platform, a company can see internal problems, forecast sales, detect certain risks sooner than later (Ex: sales agents are alerting management through the CRM that they are losing customers because competition has lowered prices), capabilities needed to build a dynamic business strategy that will react and enable fast adjustments to a changing world. In the case of the software company that implemented its new CRM, they recognized the need for better data as a strategic goal, which led to better reports, that helped the management team make better strategic decisions and increase internal efficiency, which improved sales and profitability as a result.

Business workflow automation. In the case of the B2B sales company, not only did we see that business workflows allowed that company to do things better, faster, and smarter, but they used the CRM to create automated workflows, so the CRM can be able to "think and act" according to certain predefined computer rules (workflows).

In the case of the B2B sales company which has to sell imported tulips before they reach the warehouse and distribute those tulips within 24 hours of arriving at the warehouse, questions such as: "who buys the products"; "where to deliver"; "how are they paying"; "who checks payments"; "what tulips they want"; "how many tulips"; "when they need it"; "who delivers those tulips"; "Who informs customers that delivery will be today". and so on are all information that needs to be collected as soon as possible, which is why the existence of digital process automation and digital workflows can lead to the collection of all that data in a single platform, from where they can be processed automatically, and used to increase performance and even reduce operational risks.

Challenges in CRM implementation

The challenges that those 10 companies went through to implement their CRMs can be grouped into:

- **Time** - Some CRMs are easier to implement than others. In the case of companies that have a less common way of working, such as the architecture studio, they need to allocate more time and financial resources to implement an efficient CRM, given that besides time allocated for CRM implementation they also need time to digitalize their business processes, but as this paper demonstrates, allocating the time needed to think about business processes and how they can be integrated into a CRM is a worthwhile investment.
- **Resistance to change** - In the case of the B2C telecommunication company, the biggest challenge came from employees who felt at war with technology, those salespeople felt that their job was in jeopardy if the company implemented the CRM and tried to sabotage it's implementation.
- Eventually, after the implementation of the CRM, some of these employees lost their jobs, the less efficient employees being fired shortly after the implementation of CRM. In this sense, we can say that statistically most of us will change jobs in the future, as the constant advances in technology will make most traditional jobs absolute and employees will be in a constant search for jobs that produce both job satisfaction as well as a higher added value in the business world, thus hopefully reaching higher wages.

However, this is not a bleak future, as jobs will not disappear, they will only change as they had in the past as seen in the study of Tytler, Bridgstock, White, Mather, McCandless, and Michelle Grant-Iramu (2019)

Employees will need to do meaningful and valuable work in the future, just as they do today, certainly not all employees want to change the way they do things or learn new skills, but this will become the norm in the future.

- **Time to adjust** - Some employees, such as the topography company, knew they needed a CRM, but they didn't know how to use it. In this regard, workshops and tutorials were used to help the learning process. Most employees are not afraid of technology, but of things they don't know. In this sense, a software company that produces a CRM or any other business software solution must also offer educational services, so that those employees can adapt more quickly to the correct use of various business IT platforms and not become enemies of change, due to the fear of unknown.

Final conclusions

As a final conclusion for the 10 analyzed SMEs, we can conclude that with a monthly SaaS subscription between 10 and 15 euros per user or even the payment of a one time license, the investments paid off, investments that in the all of the 10 business field area brought noticeable improvements in customer relationship and a higher organizational performance, which according to the 10 managers, justified the investment.

We hope that specialized CRM's platforms will become increasingly popular in Romanian SME's, and the insights from various studied that prove both the effective implementation of such platforms and how those implementations should be treated will help managers overcome the challenges in using a CRM.

As a final conclusion, we can say that a CRM can be a competitive advantage for Romanian businesses, because CRMs, especially offered in the monthly SaaS subscription system are financial accessible digital solutions that can increase the productivity of SMEs without any significant financial risk, but the success of implementing a CRM lies in a careful analysis of business expectations and the firm commitment of managers to make the organizational changes necessary for a successful CRM implementation.

Further research

Following direct discussions with the 10 companies, as well as experience we can say that one of the most important challenges in digitizing companies in Romania has to do with correctly conducting the

internal analysis on the current state of digitization and setting achievable expectations after the adoption of various IT platforms designed to increase organizational productivity.

In this sense, as a future research, we propose the creation of an online digital audit mechanism for Romanian companies, as a self digital diagnostic tool free to use by any manager. In the future paper, this digital diagnostic mechanism will address a sample of at least 365 Romanian companies to obtain data with statistical relevance of 95% and will look into the current degree of digitization in Romanian companies and the desired direction of digitization by Romanian entrepreneurs.

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